

Peer Pressure in Surgery: How Colleagues Determine a Physician's Treatment Style

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ABSTRACT

Background: Variation in treatment choices for similar patients is substantial and well documented in the literature, but its determinants remain unclear. Adjusting for patient characteristics explains variation only to a limited extent. Less is known about how supply-side factors, such as practice environment or heterogeneity in physicians' behaviours, drive the observed hospital or regional variation in healthcare delivery. One such area of treatment variation is hip replacement, where both cemented and uncemented prostheses are common, despite official recommendations in England in favour of the former. The aim of this study is to explore the extent to which orthopaedic surgeons' practice style or the environment in which they work determine differences in the treatment choice between cemented and uncemented hip replacements.

Data: We employ patient-level administrative data from all publicly-funded hip replacement surgeries performed in England between 2008 and 2016. These data include information on patient characteristics, clinical information and details of the admission pathway, as well as identifiers of the physician in charge of delivering care.

Empirical Strategy: We use exogenous shocks in physicians' practice environments due to job moves to estimate the impact of environment on physicians' treatment decisions within a difference-in-differences analysis framework. For each orthopaedic surgeon in England, we construct employment histories and identify those who move from one hospital to another during the study period. The practice environment is defined as the rate of cemented hip replacements for all physicians in the hospital, omitting the moving doctor's own cases. We test both i) heterogeneity in adaptation patterns to a new environment using dynamic DiD models as well as ii) non-symmetric treatment effects for physicians who move to high-cemented vs. low-cemented environments. Finally, we explore if the decision to move to a specific hospital depends on whether the practice environment is more aligned with physicians' own practice style, i.e. positive matching.

Results: Our sample includes 481,704 cases of hip replacement performed by 3,903 physicians. We have identified 124 physicians who move hospitals at some point during our study period. After the move, physicians' are 5.5 percentage points more likely to perform a cemented hip replacement for every 10 percentage point change in the practice environment. We find that physicians' practice styles change quickly after the move, with little to no further adaptation to the new environment after the first year. This suggests that the change in physicians' propensity to perform a cemented procedure after the move is mainly driven by local hospital constraints and peer effects. Furthermore, physicians respond symmetrically to increases and decreases in the hospital cemented rate. We find no evidence of endogenous move of physicians to hospitals.